

Data Analysis in R

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Previous class

- Basic introduction to RStudio
- Basic data types: character, numeric, integer, logical
- Functions
- Packages
- Vectors
- Subsetting

Data acquisition

Data visualisation

Data analysis

Hadley Wickham, [*R for Data Science*](#) (O'Reilly, 2016)

“an opinionated collection of R packages designed for data science. All packages share an underlying design philosophy, grammar, and data structures” (<https://www.tidyverse.org/>)

“**TIDY DATA** is a standard way of mapping the meaning of a dataset to its structure.”

—HADLEY WICKHAM

In tidy data:

- each variable forms a column
- each observation forms a row
- each cell is a single measurement

each column a variable

id	name	color
1	floof	gray
2	max	black
3	cat	orange
4	donut	gray
5	merlin	black
6	panda	calico

each row an observation

Data frame

- Data structure used to store tabular data
- Each column (variable) is also a vector
- Tidyverse uses the term 'Tibble'

1	"S"	TRUE
7	"A"	FALSE
3	"U"	TRUE
numeric	character	logical

Environment

History

Connections

Tutorial

Import Dataset

58 MiB

List

R

Global Environment

Data

interviews	131 obs. of 14 variables	
\$ key_ID	: num [1:131]	1 1 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 ...
\$ village	: chr [1:131]	"God" "God" "God" ...
\$ interview_date	: POSIXct[1:131], format: "2016-...	
\$ no_membrs	: num [1:131]	3 7 10 7 7 3 6 12 ...
\$ years_liv	: num [1:131]	4 9 15 6 40 3 38 7...
\$ respondent_wall_type	: chr [1:131]	"muddaub" "muddaub..."
\$ rooms	: num [1:131]	1 1 1 1 1 1 1 3 1 ...
\$ memb_assoc	: chr [1:131]	NA "yes" NA NA ...
\$ affect_conflicts	: chr [1:131]	NA "once" NA NA ...
\$ liv_count	: num [1:131]	1 3 1 2 4 1 1 2 3 ...
\$ items_owned	: chr [1:131]	"bicycle;televisio..."
\$ no_meals	: num [1:131]	2 2 2 2 2 2 3 2 3 ...
\$ months_lack_food	: chr [1:131]	"Jan" "Jan;Sept;Oc..."
\$ instanceID	: chr [1:131]	"uuid:ec241f2c-060..."

Average number of rooms in each village

Wall types

Number of people living in houses

from Data to Viz

<https://www.r-graph-gallery.com/>
<https://www.data-to-viz.com/>

- `select`
- `filter`
- `mutate`
- `group_by`
- `summarise`

Exercise 1

Using pipes, subset the interviews data set:

- Include interviews with respondents who were members of an irrigation association only (see the column 'memb_assoc')
- Retain only the columns 'affect_conflicts', 'liv_count', and 'no_meals'.

Exercise 2

Create a new dataframe from the interviews data (name it, for instance 'exercise2') that meets the following criteria:

- Contains only the 'village' column and a new column called 'total_meals'. This new column should specify the total number of meals served in the household per day on average ($\text{no_membres} \times \text{no_meals}$).
- The final dataframe should only contain the rows where 'total_meals' is greater than 20.

Summarise()

- Use this function to calculate aggregate statistics
- Example:

```
summarise(interviews,  
          avg_rooms = mean(rooms))
```

- Available functions include:

- mean()
- sd()
- max()
- min()
- n()

	avg_rooms
1	1.740458

Exercise 3

Find the mean, min, and max number of household members for each village. Also add the number of observations per village.

(hint: use `group_by()`, `summarize()` and `n()`).

Exercise 4

Answer the following questions:

- How many households in the survey have two meals per day? How many households have three meals per day? Are there any other numbers of meals represented?

(In other words: create a list of the various options for the number of meals per day, together with a count of the number of households for each of these options)

Tip: Use count()

Exercise 5

Answer the following questions:

- How many households in the survey have two meals per day? How many households have three meals per day? Are there any other numbers of meals represented?

(In other words: create a list of the various options for the number of meals per day, together with a count of the number of households for each of these options)

Tip: Use count()

Exercise 6

Can you list the villages which have a bicycle?
How many households in these villages own a bicycle?